

Collaboration Methodology in Between Logistics Clusters

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Abstract

Well-established logistics clusters, in search of bundling existing good flows with other flows in the logistics chain, still do not leverage their full potentials in terms of competitiveness and sustainability for the European industry and society. There are several reasons such as a lack of advanced collaboration practices between the local actors (i.e. shippers and transport operators) in the cluster and insufficient connectivity and coordination between European logistics clusters to maximize the full network potential of the clusters and related hubs.

One solution to address these problems is to set up a massification concept. Under the ‘massification concept’ is understood the bundling of flows of several companies (a.o. industrial shippers or retailers) for shipment to the same destination to increase the utilization of transport capacities. So, massification can bring about a more sustainable modal shift. To do so, a growth lever might be the use of tools such as the xIntermodal tool and Quick Check tool; newly developed within the H2020 Clusters 2.0 project. The Clusters 2.0 project encourages establishment logistics clusters integration into a high performing synchromodal transportation network at the EU scale and improves transport efficiency. These innovative initiatives, implemented in Clusters 2.0, comprises a wide range of advantages that constitute a strong argument to support the related mind shift in the logistics market.

Therefore, the present paper has two objectives: to develop a framework for the massification concept and to identify the success and failure elements as well as the evaluation criteria for a successful massification concept. To do this, a governance body structure is defined and gain-sharing mechanisms are reviewed. The findings firstly reveal that the success of the massification concept strongly depends on the availability and sharing of data and collaboration of different shippers. Secondly, the newly developed tools allow better mapping of the transportation flows in the European transportation network.

Keywords: Clusters 2.0; collaborative platform; horizontal collaboration; massification methodology; gain sharing;

1. Introduction

Well-established logistics clusters, in search of bundling existing good flows with other flows in the logistics chain, still do not leverage their full potentials in terms of competitiveness and sustainability for the European industry and society. There are several reasons, such as a lack of advanced collaboration practices between the local actors (i.e. shippers and transport operators) in the cluster and insufficient connectivity and coordination between European logistics clusters to maximize the full network potential of the clusters and related hubs.

H2020 Clusters 2.0 vision is to leverage the full potential of European Logistics Clusters for a sustainable, efficient and fully integrated transport system. Such vision allows making optimal use of an open network of logistics clusters operating in the frame of TEN-T and supporting local, regional and European development while keeping neutral the local impacts such as congestion, noise, land use, and local pollution levels. The concept of the project is based on a framework to enhance and advance towards better coordination between logistics actors in clusters and to improve coordination and connectivity between European logistics clusters.¹

In this paper, the focus is on the Symbiotic Network of Logistics Clusters. The aim is to establish logistics clusters integration into a high performing synchromodal transportation network at the EU scale and to improve transport efficiency. Moreover, it addresses the shift towards low-emission transport modes and consolidated freight management between logistics clusters.²

For freight planners and operators, it remains challenging and risky to make decisions about supply chain collaboration and other matters related to logistics information sharing and assets management without considering how these choices affect entire logistics and transport systems. It has been mentioned some examples to enhance co-operation at vertical as well as horizontal level to stimulate a modal shift towards low emission transport modes³.

According to Guilbault and Echo (2008), as shipments decrease in size, the need for freight consolidation and bundling increases. This consolidation already takes place at the level of individual shippers and carriers but it is still not sufficient to reach the full capacity of transportation means. This especially applies to trains, barges and freight marketplaces, whose visibility of transport demand is too short to consolidate many flows. A simulation study based on actual flows in France (around 200,000 pallets per week) already showed a great potential to mix asynchronous flows with +20% of load factor and up to 50% of volume shifted from road to rail without adding cost or lead-time (Sarraj et al. 2014).

¹ In particular, Clusters 2.0 followed a 3-phase iteration approach in which each Living Lab is driving key Clusters 2.0 solutions combined and synchronized with dedicated conceptual and methodological work to leverage synergies and to scale up Clusters 2.0 developments. The core of the Clusters 2.0 methodology is a twinning of the three Living Lab with dedicated Work Packages (www.clusters20.eu).

² Moreover, one of the main objectives of this Work Package is to develop the demand-driven roles and local governance models of smart logistics clusters composed of shippers, fourth-party logistics (4PLs) and logistics service providers (LSPs).

³ www.clusters20.eu

Tyan et al. (2003) revealed a substantial cost saving and a service level improvement of about 20% due to the implementation of a collaborative consolidation policy. Moreover, such a policy can benefit both the carrier and the shipper at the same time. According to Zhu et al. (2014), the fundamental idea of consolidation-based transportation is to group loads from different shippers, with possibly different origins and destinations, and to load them into the same vehicles for efficient long-haul transportation. However, neglecting consolidation opportunities in outbound shipment scheduling may result in the underestimation of an important managerial option for cost savings and system optimization (Lee et al. 2003). Individual companies with limited shipment volumes lack access to cost-efficient and highly productive transport networks (Leitner et al. 2011).

According to Figure 1, the freight transport by road in 2017 increased by 45% compared to the reference year 1995, while this increment for rail mode is only 8% for the same year compared to the reference year. Figure 1 demonstrates a general overview of the transportation volume of three mentioned modes of transport per year.

Figure 1: Freight transport by mode in the EU 28 (billion ton-kilometers)

Source: own composition based on European Commission, Statistical pocketbook 2019
https://ec.europa.eu/transport/facts-fundings/statistics/pocketbook-2019_en

Therefore, to make a balance between rail and road modes of transportation and reducing CO₂ emitted by road transportation, a modal shift is required, which is based on the collaboration of shippers and freight sharing. To do so, in the Clusters 2.0 project, two tools namely xIntermodal and Quick Check are developed. xIntermodal tool provides graphical information, a routing network, time schedules, and the production cost for all modes of transport to optimize intermodal routing. While Quick Check tool presents a macro view of transportation flows in the selected origin and destination.

To enhance the efficiency of the freight consolidation and bundling process, the new concept - massification methodology – has been developed. Massification is generally used in the transport plan to gather goods at one location. However, the massification concept implemented in the Clusters 2.0 project is more complex.

The massification into a logistics organization aims to bundle goods on the same transport mode with capacity and it aims to develop a new collaborative methodology and supports a group of shippers to bundle their goods on the same train towards one destination. The massification concept is widely based on the Physical Internet Concept, which highlights the bundling approach to reach an efficient, sustainable, flexible, and resilient logistics system.

Massification methodology is considered as a cluster solution to overcome three various problems namely, visibility on rail connections, the collaboration between stakeholders and visibility on transportation flows. Implementation of the massification methodology, which is a combination of xIntermodal tool, Quick Check tool, and collaboration meetings, will overcome these problems.

Figure 2: Cluster solution of massification

Source: Author's composition

Further, the massification methodology is in line with the objectives of the European Green Deal (2019). The Green Deal aims to accelerate the shift to sustainable and smart mobility and to increase the EU's climate ambition for the future.

This paper defines the objectives of the developed tools and assess the tools by SWOT analysis. Moreover, the major purpose of this paper is to offer some insight into the massification methodology implemented in the Clusters 2.0 project. Also, it will outline the theoretical framework for a successful accomplishment of the massification methodology together with success and failure elements.

The approach of this paper is demonstrated in figure 3. First, desk research has been conducted to gain knowledge of the collaborative platform and horizontal collaboration and to collect the previous research and work done on this field. As the next step, an expert meeting has been held together with a literature review to obtain the gain sharing methods. Afterward, the objectives of the developed tools such as the xIntermodal tool and Quick Check tool have been captured by showing up various demo sessions and by attending several online meetings. Then, the massification methodology has been defined which includes four main steps. Subsequently, to assess the tools, a SWOT analysis has been performed to specify the internal and external success and failure factors of each of the developed tools and the massification methodology. Finally, a confrontation matrix analysis has been fulfilled to further analyze the output of each of the SWOT analyses.

Figure 3: Framework of the paper

Source: Author's composition

The SWOT analysis is conducted according to the following steps. First, several online meetings and demo sessions are held with the developer of each tool for understanding the concept and main objectives of each tool. Second, the strengths of the tool are determined and listed; these are internal factors and are the advantages of the tool, which can bring added value to it. Third, negative aspects of each tool are identified and listed; these are inherent disadvantages of the tool. Fourth, the possible external opportunities for each tool are recognized. Fifth, the external factors, which can cause a problem for the tool, are distinguished and listed as threats.

The rest of the paper is organized in the following way. Section 2 reports a literature review regarding the collaborative platform, horizontal collaboration in logistics and gain sharing definition and methods. Section 3 describes the developed tools and analyzes them by a SWOT analysis. Section 4 describes and analyzes the massification methodology. Finally, section 5 outlines the conclusions.

2. Literature Review

The literature review is structured into three sub-sections. The first part reviews available literature related to the development of collaborative platforms. Here, the application not software perspective of collaborative platforms are considered. The second and third part provides a review of contributions that correspond to collaborative relationships in transportation and logistics and gain sharing methods, respectively.

2.1. Collaborative Platform

This section argues firstly the general definitions of the collaborative platform and two major models namely corporate and cooperative. Then, the interpretation and importance of collaborative governance in terms of the decision-making process and transportation are reviewed. In the end, the relevant research on the collaborative platform is plotted.

As a general term, collaboration refers to a “high intensity” mode of interaction (Keast et al. 2007; Ansell and Gash 2018). Moreover, collaboration is defined as a form of participation where stakeholders are jointly involved in priority setting and the planning, implementation and evaluation stages of the process, thus allowing diverse stakeholders to work together to develop a more comprehensive understanding of the situation, to attempt to resolve a conflict or to develop solutions (Koontz 2006; Davies and White 2012). De Mattos and Laurindo (2015) define the collaboration as “working together to produce something with benefits for both”. Therefore, collaboration can be a way to create value and to innovate.

Collaborative governance - as a model of collective action for achieving public purposes - refers broadly to “the processes and structures of public policy decision making and management that engage people constructively across the boundaries of public agencies, levels of government, and/or the public, private and civic spheres” (Emerson et al. 2012; Ansell and Gash, 2018). Although collaboration is based on a mutual objective, it is a self-interested process in which firms will participate only if it contributes to their survival (Simatupang and Sridharan 2002). Also, Emerson and Gerlak (2014) refer to Collaborative Governance Regimes (CGRs) to public policy or service-oriented, cross-organizational systems involving a range of autonomous organizations representing different interests and/or jurisdictions (as opposed to like-minded coalitions).

The collaborative organization extends the concepts of chains and strategic alliances, as each organization attempts to maximize its performance. According to Ansell and Gash (2018), “a collaborative platform is an organization or program with dedicated competences, institutions, and resources for facilitating the creation, adaptation, and success of multiple or ongoing collaborative projects or networks. It is often a stand-alone organization, but may also be a program or a sub-unit of an organization”. However, as negative aspects, collaborative governance can be fragile, time-consuming, and risky and can lead to the least common denominator outcomes.

There are two major governance models commonly used in practice: corporate and cooperative. The first one, the corporate governance model, is assumed adequate for centralized organizations, in which all partners act as one single integrated company to make decisions collectively. The key issue is to form the

coalition and fix the collaborative terms (Xu et al. 2012; Xu 2013). In the second one, the cooperative model, the main idea is to reach the collaborative organization performance level but in a more dynamic manner. The mechanism design theory is a theoretical framework to favor collaborative solutions without collaboration by the design of a mechanism that aligns the objectives of the players to a global objective with the help of an organizer (an auctioneer, a web platform, etc.). In that regard, the platform should follow several principles, such as neutrality, fair mechanism, and respect of business/data privacy (Xu 2013; Pan et al. 2014).

Further, collaboration is not just about developing close information exchange based relationships at an operational level of activity but also needs to be implemented at tactical and strategic levels in the organizations across the supply chain (Barratt 2004). To use collaborative governance in the decision-making process, Emerson et al. 2012; Emerson and Gerlak 2014 define collaborative governance as “the processes and structures of public policy decision making and management that engage people constructively across the boundaries of public agencies, levels of government, and/or the public, private and civic spheres to carry out a public purpose that could not otherwise be accomplished”.

The efficient use of transportation resources is particularly emphasized in the context of integrated logistical management (Lee et al. 2003). In the context of transport, the objective of a collaborative network is to consolidate logistics flows from the different supply chains. Under a given transport network, a collaborative transport planning optimization issue consists of all collaborating actors (e.g. shippers, carriers) establishing optimal transport plans collectively and mutually (Pan et al. 2019). Table 1 presents some of the recent research on the concept of a collaborative platform.

Table 1: Research on the collaborative platform

Author	Year	Research
Dullaert et al.	2009	Develop an intelligent agent-based communication support platform for multimodal transport.
Boschian et al.	2011	Specify an Integrated System (IS) devoted to the management of Intermodal Transportation Networks (ITNs) to take both tactical decisions, i.e., in an offline mode, and operational decisions, i.e., in real-time.
Demirkan and Delen	2012	Define a list of requirements for service-oriented DSS and proposed a conceptual framework for DSS in the cloud. A unique contribution of the service is its perspective on how to service the product-oriented DSS environment and demonstrate the opportunities and challenges of engineering service-oriented DSS in the cloud.
Rusich	2017	Proposes a cloud-based collaborative platform supporting decision-makers in planning and managing logistics and transportation processes in interconnected collaborative networks. In particular, the case of a Decision Support System (DSS) for the Trieste intermodal transportation network has been presented.

Source: own composition according to Dullaert et al. 2009; Boschian et al. 2011; Demirkan and Delen 2012; Rusich 2017

According to the above table, the attention related to a collaborative platform for intermodal transport has been increased. The various supportive platform has been implemented for more efficient management of transportation and logistics.

2.2. Horizontal collaboration

In this part, a general definition of horizontal and vertical collaborations are reported with the comparison between them. Then, different types and dimensions of horizontal collaboration are explained, afterward, opportunities and barriers of this collaboration are discussed. Next, horizontal collaboration in transport and logistics are defined. Subsequently, the recent projects and research related to horizontal collaboration are plotted.

There are different types of business relationships in terms of the core company. In simple terms, relationships can be formed in one of two dimensions; either vertically or horizontally. Barratt (2004) presented this concept in a very useful model (Fig. 4) in which he identified the four different potential relationship partners, suppliers, and customers on the vertical axis and competitors on the horizontal axis.

Figure 4: Horizontal vs. vertical collaboration

Source: Barratt (2004)

Based on this model, the vertical collaboration includes collaboration with customers, internally (across functions) and with suppliers, while horizontal collaboration contains a collaboration with competitors, internally and with non-competitors (Barratt, 2004). Another comparison between vertical and horizontal collaborations are provided as “while close cooperation between logistics service providers (LSPs) and customer is known as vertical cooperation, concerted practices between companies operating at the same level(s) in the market or logistic chain is defined as horizontal cooperation. (European Union, 2001; Leitner et al. 2011) and it requests them to share private information and resources in logistics (Xu et al. 2012).

Bengtsson and Kock (1999) identify four types of horizontal relationships, each with a different degree of cooperation and competition. Firstly, co-existence refers to a relationship that does not include any economic exchanges and where the companies’ goals are stipulated independently. Secondly, there is cooperation, where tight bonds exist between companies that define and pursue common goals. The third type of horizontal relationship is basic competition. This relationship is characterized by an action-reaction

pattern as companies rely on the same or comparable suppliers and target the same group of customers. Finally, there is the relationship of co-opetition, which is a common relationship for logistics companies, which cooperate horizontally (Cruijssen, 2006). Therefore, horizontal cooperation aims to identify and achieve win-win situations among two or more firms operating at the same level of the supply chain, despite whether they are competitors or not, and similar or different in terms of size (Pomponi et al. 2015).

Based on Lambert et al. (1999) and Cruijssen (2006), there are three important dimensions to categorize horizontal cooperation namely; (i) level of integration, (ii) centralization, and (iii) scope and intensity. Regarding the level of integration, three types of cooperation are identified. Table 2 plots the definition of each type.

Table 2: Three types of horizontal collaboration

Type of horizontal cooperation	Definition	Features
Type I	It consists of mutually recognized partners that coordinate their activities and planning, though to a limited degree.	The time horizon is short-term and the cooperation involves only a single activity or division of each partner company.
Type II	It is a cooperation in which the participants not merely coordinate, but also integrate part of their business planning.	The horizon is of a long though the finite length and multiple divisions or functions of the companies are involved.
Type III	The participants have integrated their operations to a significant level and each company regards the other(s) as an extension of itself.	There is no fixed end date for such cooperation. It is often referred to in the literature as 'strategic alliances'.

Source: own composition based on Lambert et al. 1999 and Cruijssen 2006

The second dimension is centralization. It is identified two organizational forms of horizontal logistics collaboration namely; centralized and decentralized. In a centralized collaboration system, where a single centralized authority makes decisions on behalf of all the collaborators; or a decentralized collaboration system, which allows collaborators to make their own independent decisions (Chang and Harrington, 2000; Daft, 2009; Khare, 2006; Xu, 2013). In a centralized horizontal logistics collaboration, a third-party organization collects the relative logistics information of all the collaborators, and make centralized decisions on operation execution and coordination among collaborators to improve the global efficiency. However, a decentralized collaboration system is a platform with specific rules, based on which all collaborators in the system make their autonomous decisions. According to the rules, collaborators decide independently their strategies (or actions to take) aiming at maximizing their profit (Xu 2013).

The third dimension is related to the scope and intensity. Zinn and Parasuraman (1997) define the intensity of a logistics-based strategic alliance as the extent of direct involvement between partners, not only in establishing the alliance but also in performing, on a day-to-day basis, the logistics services embedded in it. The dimensions of scope and intensity can be combined to create a classification of alliances based on both dimensions simultaneously such as broad or narrow scope and high or low intensity. Figure 5 demonstrates this classification based on scope and intensity.

Figure 5: Alliances classification based on scope and intensity

Source: own composition based on Zinn and Parasuraman 1997

Empirical research has indicated that generally, LSPs consider cooperation with other LSPs to be a relevant approach to decrease costs, improve services or protect market positions (Cruijssen et al. 2007; Cruijssen et al. 2010). Furthermore, fierce competition in global markets, the introduction of products with shorter life cycles, and the heightened expectations of customers have forced shippers and LSPs to invest in developing stronger and mutually beneficial relationships with each other (Cruijssen et al. 2007). An effective way for LSPs to meet customer requirements and its demands is horizontal cooperation with other, possibly competing LSPs (Raue and Wallenburg, 2013).

A management framework for horizontal collaboration can be, for instance, a stepwise framework to manage key decisions and influencing factors involved in horizontal collaboration (Verstrepen et al. 2009; Leitner et al. 2011; Audy et al. 2012; Brekalo et al. 2013). A stepwise framework can involve three stages. The first stage concerns partner selection (Cheikhrouhou et al. 2010, Raue and Wallenburg, 2013) and developing trust between partners (Pomponi et al. 2015). The studies indicated that market position, common objectives and motives, structure, and similarity of flows influenced partner selection. The second stage is devoted to implementation, including defining the partner's responsibilities, leadership, and benefits (Audy et al. 2012). Finally, the third stage concerns the long-term evolution and growth of the collaboration (Verstrepen et al. 2009). Operational governance mode, which is sometimes part of the management framework (Verstrepen et al. 2009), relates to the selection of an adequate governance model for horizontal collaboration. The governance model plays a vital role in the efficacy of collaboration (Schmoltzi and Wallenburg, 2012).

There are opportunities and barriers for horizontal collaboration in transport and logistics (Cruijssen 2006). The opportunities are divided into three main groups such as costs and productivity, customer service, and market position. Moreover, impediments and threats to horizontal cooperation relate to four areas: partners, determining and dividing the gains, unequal negotiation positions of partners, and coordination and Information & Communication Technology (ICT).

Tables 3 and 4 display the opportunities and barriers for horizontal collaboration in transport and logistics respectively.

Table 3: Opportunities for horizontal collaboration in transport and logistics

Type of Opportunities	Definition*	Relevant propositions**	Features and elements
Costs and productivity	Cooperation provides companies with a platform to access the skills and capabilities of their partners (Kogut, 1988; Westney, 1988; Hamel, 1991). In this way, they can improve their operational processes by increasing the ability to control costs and to reduce the costs of the supply chain (Gibson et al. 2002). Moreover, cooperation on non-core activities offers the potential of joint purchases (e.g. of trucks, onboard computers, and fuel) to reduce purchasing costs (Dyer and Singh, 1998).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Horizontal cooperation increases the company's productivity for core activities, e.g. decrease in empty hauling, better usage of storage facilities, etc. -Horizontal cooperation reduces the costs of non-core activities, e.g. organizing safety training, joint fuel facilities, etc. -Horizontal cooperation reduces purchasing costs, e.g. vehicles, onboard computers, fuel, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Cost reduction -Learning and internalization of tacit, collective and embedded knowledge and skills -More skilled (or more efficient use of) labor force
Customer service	Cooperation not only offers benefits such as economies of scale, skilled labor force, high R&D level and access to superior technology but also generate greater customer value-added at a lower cost (Zineldin and Bredenlw, 2003).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -LSPs can specialize while at the same time broadening their services. -LSPs can offer a better quality of service at lower costs, e.g. in terms of speed, frequency of deliveries, geographical coverage, reliability of delivery times, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Complementary goods and services -Ability to comply with strict customer requirements/Improved service -Specialization
Market position	The sheer size of the volumes involved in serving large industrial shippers sometimes prohibits LSPs from entering a tendering process on an individual basis. Horizontal cooperation is a useful tool to expand the available fleet, service range, and geographic coverage, and, as a result, to increase the number of potential customers (Bleeke and Ernst, 1995). Horizontal cooperation can be a very effective way of sharing the large investments needed for R&D projects. In this way, the uncertain payoff of these projects can be shared across the companies participating in the cooperation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Horizontal cooperation enables individual LSPs to tender with large shippers on larger contracts. -Horizontal cooperation helps to protect the company's market share. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Penetrating new markets -New product development/R&D -Serving larger customers -Protecting market share -Faster speed to market

Source: own composition according to Cruijssen 2006 and Cruijssen et al.2007

**The reader is referred to Cruijssen (2006) for further information*

*** These propositions are used for the survey in the paper of Cruijssen et al. (2007). The reader is referred to that paper for further information.*

Table 4: Barriers for horizontal collaboration in transport and logistics

Impediments	Definition*	Relevant propositions**	Features and elements
Partner selection	Analyzing a potential partner's strategic and organizational capabilities requires knowledge about its physical assets, as well as about its intangible assets and organizational capabilities (Bartlett and Ghoshal, 2004)	-It is hard to find commensurable LSPs with whom it is possible to cooperate for (non-) core activities. -It is hard to find a reliable party that can coordinate the cooperation in such a way that all participants are satisfied.	-The difference in interests, opportunistic behavior -Difficulty in finding partners with whom to cooperate -Difficulty in finding a trusted party/person to lead the cooperation -Differences in operating procedures
Determining and dividing the gains	Mistrust about the fairness of the applied allocation rule for savings has caused many horizontal logistics cooperation initiatives between shippers, and/or LSPs to marginalize or disintegrate	-It is hard for the partners to determine the benefits or operational savings due to horizontal cooperation beforehand. -Partners find it hard to ensure a fair allocation of the shared workload in advance. -A fair allocation of benefits to all the partners is essential for successful cooperation.	-Difficulty in determining the (monetary) benefits -Difficulty in establishing a fair allocation of the benefits
Unequal negotiation positions of partners	Bleeke and Ernst (1995) explain how the evolvement of the relative bargaining power of partners is the key to understanding whether or not cooperation is likely to lead to a takeover. Relative bargaining power depends on three factors: the initial strengths and weaknesses of the partners, how these strengths and weaknesses change over time, and the potential for competitive conflict. A positive attitude during the negotiations will have an important beneficial impact on the cooperation's longer-term success.	-When an LSP cooperates with commensurable companies, it becomes harder to distinguish itself. -Over time smaller companies in the partnership may lose clients or get pushed out of the market completely. -When benefits cannot be shared in a perceived fairway, the larger players will always benefit most.	-Disagreement over the domain of decisions -Unequal bargaining positions (e.g. due to size differences)
Coordination and ICT	ICT is mainly an issue for horizontal cooperation agreements of medium intensity. Low-intensity initiatives often do not require specific ICT investments and high-intensity initiatives are likely to generate sufficient revenue to pay back the required ICT investments.	Cooperation is greatly hampered by the required indispensable ICT-investments.	-High indispensable ICT costs -High additional coordinating and controlling costs -Loss of control

Source: own composition according to Cruijssen 2006 and Cruijssen et al.2007

*The reader is referred to Cruijssen (2006) for further information.

** These propositions are used for the survey in the paper of Cruijssen et al. (2007). The reader is referred to that paper for further information.

Besides, other barriers such as trust, organizational structure, and entry or exit rules are mentioned in Xu (2013). By definition, trust appears as “the expectation that vulnerable action will be fulfilled. The trust in horizontal collaboration lies in the mutual belief that global profitability is the common objective shared in the alliance”. An organizational structure defines that “Horizontal collaboration results in inter-

organizational relationships, which is under the multi-governance of collaborators and appropriate organizational structure enables efficient management of such relationship”.

In principle, in both centralized and decentralized horizontal collaborations, the entry and exit rules need to be well defined to support trust and the effectiveness of the collaboration relationship. In centralized horizontal collaboration, a selective entry rule is used to guarantee the good evolvement of the collaboration. Moreover, when participants feel unprofitable staying in the current collaboration relationship or find a more suitable one, a finely defined exit rule would provide them with an evacuation option, while at the same time minimize the disturbance for the others. However, in decentralized horizontal collaboration, a rule specifying the requirement for entering into the system is essential, to guarantee that the participants are enough qualified to contribute to the collaboration. Once a participant has fulfilled the currently contracted obligations in the collaborative system, thus he can exit freely (Xu, 2013).

Crujssen (2006) defines horizontal collaboration in transport and logistics as “*active collaboration between two or more firms that operate on the same level of the supply chain and perform a comparable logistics function on the landside*”. Moreover, horizontal collaboration has been considered as an effective practice for sustainable logistics and freight transport and it has gained increased attention in recent years. In the context of horizontal collaborative transport, collaborative network design aims at reorganizing or designing a common, shared collaborative logistics and transport network for supply chain stakeholders. Horizontal collaborative transport refers to all types of horizontal cooperation or collaboration in freight transport between players operating at the same level of the supply chain (carriers, logistics service providers, shippers or receivers), between independent supply chains, and between transport networks, from occasional cooperation to long-lasting collaboration, and from operational level to strategic level (Pan et al. 2019). In table 5, the recent projects regarding the governance model are discussed.

Table 5: Recent projects related to the governance model

Project	Year	Definition	Objectives	Outcome
Collaboration Concepts for Co-modality (CO3) - (Crujssen, 2012)	2011	The project coordinates studies and expert group exchanges and builds on existing methodologies to develop legal and operational frameworks for collaboration via freight flow bundling in Europe.	The goal of the project is to deliver a concrete contribution to increasing load factors, reducing empty movements and stimulate co-modality, through collaboration between industry partners, thereby reducing transport externalities such as greenhouse gas emissions and costs.	A consortium is only economically viable if enough synergy exists among it. Furthermore, there is the aspect of trust, fair gain sharing, and competition. Therefore, fair gain sharing is the first key message of CO3. There is a need for a specialized entity to set up, manage and develop collaboration. If such a neutral, transparent and trusted party is not present, there is a severe risk that not all parties will efficiently work together in the long run on a fair give and take basis. Given the importance of a trustee, CO3 states that in a true horizontal collaboration project, a neutral trustee must be in place.
Smart Rail project: Governance models enabling	2016	It is an innovative governance framework that is problem-driven, market-oriented and corridor based. Development of the	To understand the intra- and internetwork relations between all potential partners in a cooperative business network	It represents a vertical highly relational inter-organizational governance network in which 4PL or LSP empowered by an information-sharing platform acts as intermediary and

cooperation in the supply chain		framework followed a multidisciplinary approach taking into account network governance theory, supply chain management as well as geographical terms such as corridors and networks.	developed in the previous task and to assess the potential for its successful implementation.	governs the relationships between all partners in the network – one or more shippers, one or more logistics service providers, terminal operator, and railway freight operator. It generates a Logistical Control tower for long-distance rail freight transport. It is an operational Logistical Control Tower including rail information in operation from August 2017. It is supported by a rail-enabled CT as an information-sharing platform.
AEOLIX project	2016	AEOLIX project exploits the results of CO-GISTICS and will address new Trieste intermodal transportation network challenges. In particular, the cargo transport optimization service deployed in CO-GISTICS will be integrated with further functionalities concerning the pre-clearing paperless procedures in export.	It aims to develop a cloud-based collaborative logistics ecosystem for configuring and managing (logistics-related) information pipelines thus creating visibility across the supply chain and enabling more sustainable and efficient transport of goods across Europe.	It designs architecture for a collaborative IT infrastructure for the operational connection of logistics information systems.
SELIS project	2016	SELIS takes the concept of smart collaborative spaces in the domain of transport logistics, which has been explored in previous FP7 Projects (e-Freight, eMAR, EcoHubs, and iCargo). SELIS goes one step further by highly enhancing the technologies basis, including strong analytics and knowledge graphs, and by lowering the barriers to forming, managing and participating in virtual transportation chain communities, providing tools to support the semiautomatic configuration of collaborative nodes in the cloud, and by providing ready to be configured solution sets to support innovative business models.	It Produces a governance framework for the use of APIs, protocols, etc., taking into account organizational aspects within ‘cooperation agreements’. SELIS is aimed at delivering a platform for pan-European logistics application by: Embracing a wide spectrum of logistics perspectives and creating a unifying operational and strategic business innovation agenda for pan European Green logistics. Establishing an exceptionally strong consortium of logistics stakeholders and ICT providers.	A key advantage will be eliminating the need for centralized infrastructure with complex governance. SELIS will link private-sector platforms and public-sector platforms, promoting customs-business cooperation and supporting the seamless movement of goods through secure trade chains.

Source: own composition according to reports and deliverable of each mentioned project

As can be observed from the above table, a fair gain sharing mechanism and a trusted party are considered as the most important factors for a successful horizontal collaboration. Moreover, as the results of the

projects, the information-sharing platform between logistics service providers and all the partners in the network and is needed for an operational connection between them.

2.3. Gain Sharing

Gainsharing plans, such as the popular Scanlon plan, combine two powerful motivational tools – an employee involvement piece in which employee suggestions for cost savings are solicited, evaluated and implemented by employee–management committees, and a plant-wide group bonus in which employees and managers share in any savings generated under the plan (Graham-Moore and Ross, 1995; Lawler, 1988; Levine and Tyson, 1990; Arthur and Kim, 2005). In general, gainsharing programs offer substantial flexibility in the chosen formulas to determine the payoff and procedures for distributing gains (Welbourne and Gomez Mejia 1995).

However, gainsharing programs are inherently more risky for employees than a more traditional fixed pay system because gainsharing bonuses are contingent on achieving plant-wide cost reductions (Gomez Mejia et al. 2000; Arthur and Kim, 2005). Gainsharing is not profit sharing; the system need not have anything to do with profitability and is generally keyed to lowering costs. Moreover, gainsharing is a compensation system that aims to involve workers in improving performance and that, by way of measurement, shares between labor and management the financial gains made (Weiss 2006).

When costs and gains are generated as a result of a cooperation between different partners, it is not trivial to determine which partner has a right to which fraction of these gains and which partner should pay what part of the coalition cost. To properly divide these costs or profits among all the collaborating partners a gain sharing method to be selected (Defryn 2017). The gain sharing (or cost allocation) issue concerns how to fairly allocate the common gain (or cost) to collaborating players (Pan et al. 2019). The gain sharing problem can be extended to the coalition stability problem since the sharing scheme is crucial to coalition stability (Audy et al. 2012; Pan et al. 2019).

According to Defryn (2017), among numerous methods regarding gain sharing in the literature, the most important and commonly used ones are reported in the following table. The methods based on the fundamentals of cooperative game theory are Shapley value and Nucleolus, while, Equal profit method, Alternative cost avoided method and Volume-based allocation are considered as rules of thumb.

Table 6: Different methods of gainsharing

Method	Definition
Shapley value	This method is based on a partner’s cooperative productivity since it takes into account the marginal effect of a partner on all sub-coalitions. The need for information is the main drawback of this method. The calculation of the Shapley value requires at least an estimation of the total cost or benefit of every possible sub-coalition.
Nucleolus	The nucleolus is an allocation mechanism based on the idea of minimizing the maximum unhappiness of each partner. The nucleolus is more difficult to compute than the Shapley value and for larger groups of collaborators though, this calculation becomes very time-intensive.
Equal Profit Method	The method based on the idea of obtaining relative savings as equal as possible for the partners. The calculation is done by solving a straightforward linear program that minimizes the largest relative savings difference between any pair of partners. It can be mentioned that it might seem fair to offer the same relative savings to every partner in the coalition. However, the profit allocated to each partner strongly depends on its stand-alone cost. As a result. Companies with a higher stand-alone cost will receive a larger absolute part of the coalition gain.

Alternative cost avoided method	An allocation method is based on the principle of first dividing the total coalition gain in a separable and non-separable part. The Alternative cost avoided method defines a set of weights that can be used to divide the non-separable costs based on the individual contributions of each partner. These weights are based on the difference between the stand-alone cost and the marginal cost of a partner.
Volume-based allocation	The total coalition costs are divided by calculating a weight for each partner and when a volume-based allocation is used, the weights are based on the volume shipped by the partner concerning the total coalition volume.

Source: own composition according to Schmeidler (1969), Tijs and Driessen (1986), Frisk et al. (2010), Defryn (2017)

The relevant features for each method of gainsharing are summarized in table 7.

Table 7: characteristics of each gainsharing's method

	Shapley value	Nucleolus	Alternative cost avoided method	Equal Profit Method	Volume-based allocation
Efficiency	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Individual Rationality	Yes	Yes	Yes	-	-
Stability	-	Yes	-	-	-
Additivity	Yes	-	-	-	-
Dummy Player	Yes	Yes	-	-	-
Symmetry	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	-

Source: own composition according to Schmeidler (1969), Tijs and Driessen (1986), Frisk et al. (2010), Defryn (2017)

It can be mentioned that the Shapley value and the Alternative cost avoided methods are preferential. The Shapley value should be used for smaller, coherent groups. The Alternative cost avoided method is very suitable for collaborations of changing partners. To ensure a fair gain sharing mechanism, the marginal contributions of each LSP to the total gain have to be accurately quantified. These can then be allocated using concepts from cooperative game theory (Crujssen 2006).

3. Developed tools

Knowing that massification can lever modal shift, to do this, two different tools are developed in the Clusters 2.0 project such as xIntermodal and Quick Check. In this section, the objectives of each model are explained and SWOT analysis is performed for each developed tool.

3.1. PTV xIntermodal tool; Intermodal routing and optimization

The web-based tool developed by PTV AG⁴ company provides the graphical user interface to interact with the xIntermodal routing service. The xIntermodal routing service integrates various aspects of routing network, time schedules, the production cost for all modes of transport to optimize intermodal routing. PTV xIntermodal server enables to design an intermodal routing taking various transportation modes into account as follows: deep/short sea; rail; road; inland navigation; air.

The intermodal routing and optimization module generate (intermodal) routing alternatives (transport chains) based on existing timetable-based transport services. Transport orders are assigned to a valid intermodal network in an optimum way considering concrete transport capacities (synchro-modality) such as transport modes: road, rail, inland waterways (barge), sea, air; terminals (including intra-terminal connection); (intermodal) transport operators; regular transport services including cost; time table based intermodal routing alternatives (transport chains); emission calculation for transport chain alternatives based on (real) average, standard or calculated basic parameters (e.g. interface to calculation services possible); latest pickup (at first location) – earliest delivery (at final location); optimized allocation of orders to (intermodal) transport services considering capacity limitations and minimizing costs; integrated optimization by solver engine (GUROBI).

3.1.1. Objectives and implementation

PTV xIntermodal follows three main objectives; (i) calculation of all relevant transport chain alternatives taking into consideration any mode available, (ii) assignment of transport orders to intermodal transport services available considering time restrictions, costs, and capacities, (iii) planning component for the integration into existing transport management or other system environments. To do so, several steps should be respected such as:

- *Step 1:* Calculation of all relevant transport chain door-to-door or terminal-to-terminal alternatives taking into consideration any mode available.
- *Step 2:* Routing properties
- *Step 3:* Calculation of all relevant transport chain alternatives and itinerary per alternative

⁴ PTV (Planung Transport Verkehr) AG is a German company specialising in software solutions and consulting services for traffic and transportation, mobility, and logistics. The German company PTV (Planung Transport Verkehr AG is a member of PTV Group.

Figure 6: transport chain alternatives of a selected route

- Step 4: Assignment of transport orders to intermodal transport services available considering time restrictions, costs, and capacities.
- Step 5: Possibility to dynamically manage capacities

3.1.2. Use cases

Based on the transportation modes, some use cases can be carried out such as planning and execution and strategic intermodal planning. Each use case is explained in table 8.

Table 8: Use cases of xIntermodal tool

Planning and execution		Strategic intermodal planning	
Feature	Definition	Feature	Definition
<i>Intermodal Chain Composition</i>	It provides a quick and easy calculation of alternative connections taking schedules and costs into account. Moreover, calculating emissions for the green footprint is provided.	<i>Strategic Planning</i>	It calculates and compares alternative routes according to the valid combinations of transportation modes and CO2 emissions which makes decisions easy to select the optimum routes concerning times and costs.
<i>Intermodal Planning System</i>	It provides a quick and easy calculation of alternative connections for transport orders and also integrated intermodal planning of orders. Transport orders can be allocated and optimized based on time and costs.	<i>Network Simulation and Assessment</i>	It carries out network simulation and assessment with the following objectives: comparing operator and network performance; elaborate different scenarios finding an optimum flow of goods; strategic planning for analyzing optimum intermodal routings taking customer-specific constraints into account.
<i>Exception Handling</i>	A comprehensive exception handling is provided to avoid penalties in cases of delay or any other unexpected event by		

checking alternative possibilities (time schedules, other routes/combination/service providers).

Source: Own composition based on the guideline of the tool

3.1.3. SWOT Analysis

To assess this tool, a SWOT analysis is performed. In this analysis, strengths, weaknesses of this tool are explained by mentioning opportunities and threats, which can affect the success rate of this tool in the future perspective.

Table 9: SWOT analysis of PTV xIntermodal tool

Strengths	Weaknesses
Providing alternative available connections such as rail, road, water, and air between selected origin and destination. Calculation of transportation cost for all the alternative available transportation modes Calculation of CO ₂ emission Strategic analysis of the results	Lack of knowledge of the connection between rails Fragmented information (time-consuming to collect)
Opportunities	Threats
It can be applied in the massification concept Enhancing a better and efficient supply chain management and decision-making process by the provision of strategic analysis of the results	Lack of sufficient volume of some of the shippers Availability of data in a routine time-schedule Lack of enough enthusiasm from shippers to collaborate

The main strengths of this tool are firstly presenting various options of transport modes and calculation of transportation costs for all the alternative options. Moreover, this tool can be used in the massification methodology. However, the main negative aspect of this tool is the lack of availability of updated data in a schemed way.

3.1.4. Confrontation Matrix

A confrontation matrix analysis is performed to further analyze the output of the SWOT analysis.

Table 10: Confrontation matrix analysis of PTV xIntermodal tool

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	Workshops and training on xIntermodal as part of massification workshops. Help to target ecological compliance by calculation of emissions for the transport chain and spotting ecological friendly alternatives / complimentary to European Green Deal actions. Strategic discussion and community building.	As part of the massification workshops, intermodal data can be collected. Intermodal potential can be identified to support industry and policymakers to improve intermodal transport. It can support data standardization, data collection, and data sharing by setting up agreements and pushing forward standardization for intermodal data.

Threats

xIntermodal comes along with a certain data basis on intermodal data, e.g. network and selected timetables.

xIntermodal can present the positive effects of modal shift in means of monetary and ecological savings

For sharing the data in a trusted manner, data sovereignty is given by xIntermodal, the data owner determines if to share their data set to the public or to disclose it.

There is no data concentrator for intermodal data at large in place currently, however, xIntermodal builds upon the community and shared data and by the expansion of the clusters network, data collection of new/additional data can be enabled through the clusters massification approach.

To have a better application of the xIntermodal tool, various demo and training sessions need to be held to attract more partners. This tool can increase intermodal transport by providing different alternative transport modes. However, data collection and data standardization are the main negative aspects of this tool. To solve these issues, the planned workshops can be useful to collect the data.

3.2. Quick Check tool

The second developed tool is the Quick Check tool, developed by Argusi BV in cooperation with Armines. The Quick Check tool is an online tool in which a user can search for transport synergy opportunities within Europe. It starts at an aggregate level to enable the user to quickly investigate on which lanes there is volume to collaborate on transport. The user defines the lane by selecting two locations and the radius for an area around it, after which the tool determines all transport between the two areas. From the transport, it determines the potential collaboration opportunities, where the aim of the collaboration is twofold: (1) To combine volumes to have a better fill rate of trucks; (2) To combine volumes to be able to fill a train. Both aims will support a reduction in costs and emissions. The tool will generate a report to show the changes in volume, costs, emissions and savings for different collaborations.

Figure 7: General view of the Quick Check tool

3.2.1. Data used

Based on an analysis of European transport data (Eurostat, 2015) a database is filled with transport volumes between NUTS2 regions. As the tool aims to find volumes that can be transported more efficiently by road or shift to rail, there are a few filters on the transport data:

- Only flows in or between countries of the EU28 plus Switzerland are used.
- Only road transport is included.
- Only NST product groups⁵ that are suitable for collaboration are included.
- Only transports between NUTS2 regions are included (the loading region is not equal to the unloading region).
- Only flows over 10 tons transported per year are used.

Figure 8: Road transport (ton-km) from and to NUTS2 regions along with Ten-T road corridors

3.2.2. Costs and emissions calculation

Calculating the savings of collaboration is done in two steps: (1) the savings from combining transport in trucks; (2) the savings from using the train instead of the truck. Only the cost calculation is given below, the emissions are calculated similarly.

1. *Cost savings of collaboration using truck only:*
 - a. Calculate the individual costs for each company (unitary costs multiplied by the number of trucks).
 - b. Calculate the empty trucks for each company in each direction.
 - c. Sum up companies' empty trucks for each direction, i.e. total empty trucks from A to B and from B to A. The empty trucks that can be saved are equal to the minimum of the empty trucks from A to B and from B to A.

⁵ GT04, GT05, GT08, GT10, GT11, GT13, GT15, GT17, GT18;
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/ramon/nomenclatures/index.cfm?TargetUrl=LST_NOM_DTL&StrNom=CL_NST2007&StrLanguageCode=EN&IntPcKey=&StrLayoutCode=HIERARCHIC

- d. Calculate the cost savings by multiplying the empty trucks saved by the unitary cost.
2. *Cost savings of collaboration using train:*
 - a. Calculate the number of trains in each direction.
 - b. Calculate the collaborative truck costs of the volume that fits the trains.
 - c. Recalculate the collaborative truck costs of the volume that remains transported by truck.
 - d. Calculate the collaborative train costs, including empty train runs.
 - e. Calculate the cost savings by subtracting the collaborative train costs from the collaborative truck costs of the train weight.

3.2.3. Given Insights

The tool reports the weights, costs, and emissions for the transported volume on the selected lane per organization (each NST product group is labeled as an organization). The user can then make a selection of organizations, i.e. a collaboration, to see the (in)balance in transported volumes in opposite directions and to see the savings that can be achieved by collaborating with these organizations. The savings are constructed from the costs and emissions without collaboration, with collaboration using trucks and with collaboration using trucks and trains. Furthermore, the tool shows the different route options for different transport modes. This is where the Quick Check tool connects with the xIntermodal tool.

3.2.4. SWOT analysis

The Quick Check tool is tested and SWOT analysis is made and plotted in Table 11 in a similar way as xIntermodal tool.

Table 11: SWOT analysis of Quick Check tool

Strengths	Weaknesses
The model covers the origins and destinations in most parts of Europe	The model focuses on road transport (potentially shifted to rail), it hence does not include all modes of transportation,
Easy comparison of different collaborations	The results are given in tons, however, other units like TEU would be more recognizable and easier to provide.
Calculation of track imbalance, costs, and CO ₂ emissions	The information concerning route options for rail transport is limited due to a lack of data.
Visualization of the results: The results are shown in graphs and tables	
Opportunities	Threats
It is linked to the xIntermodal tool which can lead to better use of the massification concept.	Lack of data availability: the input data is based on aggregated data and the model uses assumptions.
Supporting supply chain management and decision-making process.	Difficult to get enthusiasm from shippers to collaborate.
Low-level input is required which can lower the barriers to	

investigate collaboration opportunities.

Improving analysis and generate insights by using real shipment data.

As a positive point and similar to the xIntermodal tool, the Quick Check tool calculated CO₂ emission. Also, it provides the possibility of comparing the cost among the shippers. However, as negative points, the tool does not cover all the modes of transportation and there is a lack of availability of data to implement the tool.

3.2.5. Confrontation Matrix

In parallel, a confrontation matrix analysis is performed to further analyze the output of it.

Table 12: Confrontation matrix analysis of Quick Check tool

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	Low-level input and easy and clear analysis can lower barriers to investigate collaboration opportunities. It helps to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal.	Improving data quantity and quality will improve insights and better support decision-making.
Threats	Using public data the tool can be broadly disseminated which increases the use and feedback received and in turn, can improve the data and insights	Enhancing data quantity and quality will improve the insights and increase the trust in the results to convince the potential users. Demo and training sessions on this tool as part of massification workshops.

4. Massification methodology; Collaboration within clusters and shippers

This section aims to explain and to particularize how a collaborative methodology within logistics clusters could be built towards the introduction of the innovative concept of the “massification” project. Moreover, the definition of the massification concept is explained in detail.

4.1 Background

Horizontal collaboration requires that multiple independent shippers pro-actively work together in clusters or communities to “bundle” their overlapping freight flows. “Bundling” in this context means that the compatible freight flows of the shippers are consolidated in space, as well as synchronized in time (CO3 2014). Complex bundling networks strongly rely on the speed and cost-effectiveness of the transfers at intermediate terminals. According to Konings et al. (2008), the bundling of cargo typically involves several layers, starting with the consolidation of parcels onto a pallet and going up to the bundling of a large number

of containers onto a trunk line at sea or in the hinterland. Figure 9 depicts four types of complex bundling networks that can be used as an alternative to direct point-to-point container services.

Figure 9: Different types of complex bundling networks

Source: Konings et al. 2008

Networks B up to E rely on route bundling in intermediate or transfer terminals. The advantages of complex bundling are higher load factors and/or the use of larger transport units in terms of TEU (twenty-foot equivalent unit) capacity and/or higher frequencies and/or more destinations served. The main disadvantages of complex bundling networks are the need for extra container handling at intermediate terminals (higher transit time, increased risk of damage), longer transport distances and a higher dependency on service quality (Konings et al. 2008).

According to Tyan et al. (2003), shipment consolidation is the process of grouping different shipments from suppliers into a large shipment at the consolidation point. The motive behind consolidation is to take advantage of lower transportation rates through better utilization of a vehicle's capacity. Other advantages of shipment consolidation are mentioned by Lee et al. (2003) such as (i) to take advantage of the decreased per-unit freight costs due to the economies of scale inherent in transportation and (ii) careful planning by management to combine small outbound shipments into one large load can considerably reduce distribution costs. The performance and profitability of such a system depend in large part on the efficient and coordinated terminal and long-haul transport operations, as well as an offering of services meeting the cost and quality criteria of its potential customers (Zhu et al. 2014). At the strategic level, bundling problems are related to infrastructure construction, which is aimed at providing access between different transport

flows. Then, tactical problems concern about how to use the infrastructure, such as when and where to concentrate or split the flows.

4.2. Methodology and approach

Nowadays, massification is generally used in the transport plan to gather goods at one location. The massification concept implemented in the Clusters 2.0 project is more complex. Indeed, the massification into a logistics organization aims to bundle goods on the same transport mode with a capacity.

The massification is about bundling the flows of several companies (industrial shippers or retailers) for shipment to the same destination to increase the utilization of transport capacities. The “*massification*” concept, implemented into the Clusters 2.0 project, is based on using the modal shift to encourage companies towards a new way of shipping and a new way of perceiving its logistics organization (Figure 10). The massification project has been under experimentation since 2015 in the Hauts-de-France region with the support of Euralogistic⁶.

The massification project started in 2015 as a response to a demand of a shipper expected a regional logistics cluster support to identify other shippers with a similar need. Nonetheless, achieving such an increment could be feasible only if other shippers would commit to loading goods on the same train.

Figure 10: Massification concept

Source: Authors' composition

Indeed, the massification of flows does not narrow or constrain logistics flow bundling. It deals with collaboration between groups of stakeholders. The massification pilot aims to develop a new collaborative methodology and supports a group of shippers to bundle their goods on the same train towards one destination (Figure 11).

⁶ Euralogistic is the regional logistics cluster, which aims to promote logistics and supply-chain companies.

Figure 11: Massified flows on the train

Source: Authors' composition

Although, massification methodology can be applied to various modes of transport such as road, rail, and waterway, however, the rail mode has been chosen for the first experiment due to the location of Euralogistic and shippers on/next to the Delta 3 platform, the biggest trimodal indoor platform in France.

Therefore, it is relevant to test the concept on the railway as the “massified transport mode”. However, the logistics community seems to be reluctant to adopt the massification approach in its logistics organization due to several reasons: (i) overall lack of multimodal transport knowledge in Small and Medium Enterprises and sometimes in Key Accounts, (ii) the high cost of break loading, (iii) rail freight is not sufficiently flexible (organization, delivery, controls), (iv) rail freight suffers steadily from a lack of reliability and its long and complicated administrative procedures, (v) rail freight demands a new organization in the whole supply chain. Even if the massification project yearns for demonstrating the feasibility of a rail shift, nowadays the combined rail and barge remain under-utilized due to a lack of awareness.

The massification experiment followed a collaborative round table meeting methodological approach⁷, towards the organization of consecutive face-to-face meetings. The methodology of the massification project is defined regarding an experimentation process. Within a logistics cluster, regional shippers are invited to adopt common rules to better synchronize and optimize their logistics flows. The developed methodology will demonstrate the benefit of bundling volumes on the same train to shippers. To set up the massification project, it is gathered a sufficient number of relevant stakeholders. The identification of relevant stakeholders is defined according to several criteria: such as the size of shippers (volumes); geographic area: regional level; the range of shippers; the level of rail freight awareness. After organizing meetings with shippers, there are four main steps for the implementation of the massification concept.

⁷ For further information regarding the details of the meetings, the reader is referred to the following link: [http://www.clusters20.eu/clusters-2-0-deliverables/ D3.3 Collaboration methodology within logistics clusters](http://www.clusters20.eu/clusters-2-0-deliverables/D3.3%20Collaboration%20methodology%20within%20logistics%20clusters)

Figure 12: General framework of massification methodology: **Main steps**

Source: Authors' composition

The objective of the first step is to encouraging shippers for collaboration to bundle flows. For the second and third steps, assessment of the most relevant destination throughout data analysis (Quick Check and xIntermodal) and introduction of logistics stakeholders to operate the door-to-door logistics are the most important goals. Finally, in step 4, defining the gain sharing model and partnership agreement are the main goals. Concerning the mentioned steps, the general framework of the massification methodology is explained in the below table.

Table 13: General framework of massification methodology: **Approach**

Step1: Introduction and convincing step	Step 2: Data provision	Step 3: Group Commitment	Step 4: Implementation and collaboration
Detail of each step			
Step 1A : Energize & Influence	Step 1B: Data collection	Step 2: Consolidation	Step 3: Matching demand & supply
Objectives of each step			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To Present the massification concept - To Introduce the xIntermodal tool - To discuss with shippers to seize their sake - To ask shippers to provide data to assess the trade lane - To set up with shippers and agenda and schedule the next meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To call shippers for asking data - To send a confidential agreement - To send excel sheet template - Consolidation of data - Data analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To Present the data analysis - To discuss on highlighted connection - To provide an agreement on the destination - To shape the group of shippers who want to be involved -To provide a collective definition of next steps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To discuss their expectations and needs (frequency, number of containers, pre and post-shipment, cost, customs...) - To map shippers' warehouses (origin and destination) - To involve rail operators and LSPs (a sample of them to keep neutral)
The input of each step			
Shippers' attendees	Shippers' data	Massification map	LSPs / Rail Operators
			LSPs - Rail Operators

			attending focus lanes	Shippers
The output of each step				
Agreement to share DATA to cluster owner	Massification map	Alignment on focus lanes	Rail offering (total)	Transaction / Agreement
The tool of each step				
- xIntermodal - Own website	Quick Check	- xIntermodal -Quick Check	- Quick Check - xIntermodal	-----

Source: Authors' composition

The benefits of the massification concept can be divided into two main classes; company level and policy level (broader industry). Moreover, the stakeholders who benefit from this concept are categorized into four parts; shipper, terminal, rail operator and society. The following table describes the benefits of each level assigned for each stakeholder.

Table 14: Benefits of massification methodology

Company-level	Beneficiary stakeholder
Access to capacity	Shipper; Rail operator
Service level	Terminal; Rail operator
Transport cost savings	Shipper; Society
More rail volume	Terminal; Rail operator
Asset utilization	Terminal; Rail operator
Logistics schemes optimization	Shipper
Intermodal network visibility	Shipper; Rail operator; Terminal
Broader Industry (Policy level)	Beneficiary stakeholder
Less congestion	Shipper; Society
Sustainable transport	Shipper; Rail operator; Terminal; Society
Collaboration between stakeholders	Shipper; Rail operator; Terminal; Society
Modal shift	Shipper; Society

Source: Authors' composition

4.3. SWOT Analysis

To assess this methodology, a SWOT analysis is performed. In this analysis, strengths, weaknesses of this method are explained by mentioning opportunities and threats, which can affect the success rate of this tool in the future perspective. Table 15 plots the SWOT analysis of the massification methodology.

Table 15: SWOT analysis of massification methodology

Strengths	Weaknesses
Increasing the efficiency of the freight system which can lead to a reduction of congestion in the road system	The complexity of finding the proper combination of cargo volume and cargo types,
Reducing the transport cost as the costs are divided per unit	The complexity of using the railway mode because of a multiplicity of stakeholders: rail operators, rail companies, terminal operators, leasing, typology of boxes, container renters,
Increasing the filling rate with a TEU	Costly transportation mode compared to the truck. Arguments for shifting transportation mode have to be solid.
Optimizing logistics schemes that enable more flexibility with the use of different freight modes => higher reliability.	
Less noise since the road freight is reduced.	
Massification fosters collaboration models to access to capacity	
Opportunities	Threats
Using the modal shift to encourage suppliers towards a new way of shipping => A shift to a smoother transport mode remains inevitable to reduce emission	Lack of availability and access to data => To determine a good business model, shippers have to provide data that remain sensitive and often confidential. It brings more complexity to the massification approach.
Reduction of energy consumption and pollutant emission per ton-km for door-to-door connections with the use of intermodal freight.	The collaboration is only dependent on the collaboration of shippers and without commitment between shippers, the massification cannot work.
Massification brings more visibility to intermodal and bundling opportunities.	Market acceptance: a mind shift is inevitable since transport plans are broadly shaken up with railway mode.
	Without sufficient volumes, the massification brings no sense.
	Backward flows should be taken into account.
	Defining the most suitable gain sharing model.

As can be seen from the SWOT analysis, the main barriers of implementation of massification methodology are, first, lack of enthusiasm and strong collaboration among shippers to provide data and, secondly, a mind shift or market acceptance is required to fulfill this methodology properly. However, improving the performance of the freight system and enhancing the supply chain and logistics and next to that increasing the filling rate with a TEU are considered as the most advantages of the massification methodology.

4.4. Confrontation Matrix

For the massification methodology, also, a confrontation matrix analysis is performed to further analyze the output of the SWOT analysis, which helps to capture the best strategy of the massification methodology.

Table 16: Confrontation matrix analysis of massification methodology

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	<p>It is a new methodology to encourage the modal shift.</p> <p>Awareness-raising meeting on massification aimed at all logistics stakeholders.</p> <p>Highlighting of possible connections via the developed tools (xIntermodal tool and Quick Check tool).</p> <p>Demonstrate the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and possible financial savings through massification.</p>	<p>Streamlining of contact chains: only one contact point.</p> <p>Creation of partnership with a written agreement.</p> <p>Use of clusters to raise awareness and bring together.</p> <p>Impact of European policy (European green deal) on the logistics of the future.</p> <p>Communication is good practice.</p>
Threats	<p>Collaboration fosters access to intermodal capacities at a lower price with higher reliability.</p> <p>The collaboration of a neutral body.</p> <p>Anonymizing data.</p> <p>Asking for flows from point A to point B without precise details</p> <p>Signature of a confidentiality agreement.</p> <p>Feasibility study (technical and economic).</p> <p>Drafting and signing of a commercial contract between stakeholders.</p>	<p>Inevitable awareness of all stakeholders to drive to collaboration.</p> <p>Identify a leader who will know how to lead the group until the implementation of mass flows.</p> <p>Communicate a lot between group members.</p> <p>Motivating stakeholders.</p> <p>Fighting the resilience of logistics stakeholders to change.</p>

The success of the implementation of the massification methodology can be enhanced by strong collaboration between the shippers, which leads to the reduction of air pollution in the road network, an increase of modal shift and an increase of transport efficiency. Besides, motivated stakeholders who can communicate between clusters are other important factors. However, data needs to be collected and provided in a trusted and anonymized manner preferably through a neutral body.

5. Conclusion

The expansion of horizontal collaboration into multidimensional collaboration is needed, as the Clusters 2.0 project does not aim to drive horizontal collaboration in between two shippers on a single transportation lane, but targets to expand this into collaboration within and in between logistics clusters involving multiple stakeholders, like shippers, LSPs, railway operators and railway terminals. In this paper, various definitions of horizontal collaboration have been explained. It is observed that in the context of transport and logistics, horizontal collaboration is defined as an active collaboration between two or more firms that operate on the same level of the supply chain and perform a comparable logistics function on the landside. Concerning gain sharing methods, it can be mentioned that the Shapley value and the Alternative cost avoided methods

are preferential. The Shapley value should be used for smaller, coherent groups. The Alternative cost avoided method is very suitable for collaborations of changing partners.

This paper attempted to shed light on the massification methodology between logistics clusters and the theoretical framework for the accomplishment of this concept, which enhances horizontal collaboration among the logistics system and improving supply chain management. Further, it raises some significant points regarding two developed tools in the Clusters 2.0 project, namely, xIntermodal and Quick Check. It was found that according to the SWOT analysis of each model that lack of availability and access to data and more importantly lack of interest or enthusiasm of shippers are considered as the most significant threats in the future. However, the applicability of these models and their combination in the massification methodology are recognized as the most promising opportunity. Also, the developed tools provide alternative available connections such as rail, road, water, and air between origin and destination. It also calculates the transportation cost for all the alternative options and CO₂ emission, which is a great advantage of using the tools.

This paper demonstrated the potential of the massification methodology to remain a solution to encourage the shift to intermodal freight. Shippers with low volumes will not be attracted by intermodal solutions regarding all barriers (cost, complex organization, load factor, etc.) while with several shippers, it is possible to access relevant capacities. Though, massification is an answer to push forwards multimodal transport. One of the main results of applying the massification methodology is increasing the efficiency of the freight system, which can lead to the reduction of congestion and air pollution in the road network.

The development of a collaboration methodology within a cluster has to be deployed throughout the experiment of the massification project. Bundling goods flows on the same train relies strongly on the group of the shippers' willingness to collaborate. If no collaboration is achieved, the massification approach will not be feasible, since the essence of the project relies on commitment and collaboration. This can be considered the most significant threat and barrier of the massification methodology. According to SWOT analysis, it can be concluded that the success of the massification concept strongly depends on the availability and sharing of data and collaboration of different shippers. Moreover, it is observed that developed tools make possible an overview of the transportation flows in the European transportation network which improves the supply chain management in the European TEN-T network. Furthermore, as a result of employing the tools, available intermodal services between origin and destination in the transportation network are provided.

As discussed, several stakeholders take the benefit of the massification methodology; shippers, terminal operators, rail operators, and society. Shippers will have benefits by paying less transportation cost and also by having the visibility on the intermodal network which help them to have access to more capacity. Terminal and rail operators take advantage of having more cargo volumes which lead to asset utilization. Besides, it strengthens collaboration between stakeholders and modal shift.

Moreover, by providing a more sustainable and efficient transport network, all the stakeholders especially the society are the beneficiaries. Reduction of air pollution and less congestion on the road network are other benefits for society.

Further, this paper supports policy-making decisions to consider the best intermodal route and its alternatives for each origin and destination by applying the developed tools. Moreover, it provides benefits for academia and scholars by introducing and capturing the concept of massification methodology.

The concept of massification through cluster coordination needs to be tested in the relevant Living Lab through massification workshops at the different railway terminals, maritime ports, and airports to promote intermodal transportation and multidimensional collaboration to drive a modal shift for the shippers, which are active in the cluster. Further research is required to apply the massification methodology in other regions and TEN-T hubs in Europe and also in other transportation modes such as road and waterway. To do so, broad desk research and several meetings and workshops are needed to assess the potential of success of the massification methodology and to increase the willingness of the shippers to collaborate.

Acknowledgment

Clusters 2.0 project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 723265.

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